

STUDY OF TOPOLOGICAL GAMES OVER SOME SPECIAL PRODUCTS AND ITS FUZZIFICATION

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Abstract—In this present paper, we study topological games over some special products and its fuzzification.

Index Terms—Fuzzy Logic, Statistical Profiler, MATLAB.

I. Introduction

By introducing the concept of topological game over an ideal of Hausdorff space, a game over some special product space is played. Fuzzy set theory has been applied to fuzzify some of the results obtained. Over an ideal of a topological space has played a topological game which is explained here in brief. Also by introducing the concept of rectangle in topological product spaces, some special types of products called D-Product and C-Product are studied and a game is played over such products. Lastly, it is explained how fuzzy set theory can be applied to obtain better results [1-2].

II. GAMES OVER AN IDEAL

Let $G(I, X)$ be an infinite positional game of pursuit and evasion over I where X is a topological space and $I \subset P(X)$ s.t. (i) I is closed with respect to union (ii) I possess hereditary property [3].

Such collection I is called an ideal over X .

This game is played as follows: There are two players- P (Pursuer) and E (Evader). They choose alternately consecutive terms of a sequence $\langle E_n/n \in \mathbb{N}$, Where $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n, \dots\}$ of subsets of X s.t. each player knows I , E_0, E_1, \dots, E_n when he is choosing E_{n+1} .

A sequence $\langle E_n \rangle$ of subset of X is said to be a play of the game if for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ the following holds:

- (i) $E_0 = X$ (ii) $E_1, E_3, E_5, \dots, E_{2n+1}$ are the choice of P .
- (iii) $E_1, E_3, E_5, \dots, E_{2n+1} \in I$.
- (iv) $E_2, E_4, E_6, \dots, E_{2n+2}$ are the choice of E .
- (v) $E_1, E_2, \subset E_0, E_3, E_4 \subset E_2; \dots, E_{2n+1}, E_{2n+2} \subset E_{2n}$
- (vi) $E_1 \cap E_2 = \emptyset, E_3 \cap E_4 = \emptyset, \dots, E_{2n+1} \cap E_{2n+2} = \emptyset$.

If $\bigcap \langle E_{2n} \rangle = \emptyset$ then player P wins the play, otherwise Evader wins the play.

A finite sequence $\langle E_m/m \leq n \rangle$ is admissible for the game if the sequence $\langle E_0, E_1, \dots, E_n, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \dots, \emptyset \rangle$ is a play of the game. For admissible sequence

$\langle E_0, \dots, E_n \rangle$ and even if $s: \langle E_0, \dots, E_n \rangle \subset P(X)$ and $s(\langle E_0, \dots, E_n \rangle) = E_{n+1}$ then s is a strategy for player P . In case of odd n , s is said to be a strategy for evader E .

A strategy s is said to be winning for player P in the game $G(I, X)$ if P wins each play of the game with the help of this s . Similarly, s is said to be winning for E if E wins each play of the game with the help of s [4].

We denote by $P(I, X)$ the set of all winning strategies of P in the game $G(I, X)$ and by $E(I, X)$, the set of all winning strategies of E in the game $G(I, X)$.

A topological space X is said to be I -like if the set of all winning strategies of player is not empty i.e., if $P(I, X) \neq \emptyset$.

Similarly, a space X is said to be determined, if $P(I, X) \neq \emptyset$ or $E(I, X) \neq \emptyset$ i.e., if X is I -like or X is anti I -like.

III. RECTANGULAR PRODUCTS

A subset $A \times B$ of a topological product space $X \times Y$ is called a rectangle. A rectangle E is said to be:

- (i) Co-zero if E' & E'' are co-zero in $X \times Y$;
- (ii) Zero if E' & E'' are zero in $X \times Y$;
- (iii) Open if E' & E'' are open in $X \times Y$;
- (iv) Closed if E' & E'' are closed in $X \times Y$;

where E' & E'' are the projections of E into X and Y respectively so that $E = E' \times E''$.

A topological product $X \times Y$ is said to be strongly rectangular if each locally finite open cover of $X \times Y$ has a locally finite refinement by co-zero rectangles.

From above definitions the following conditions are seen to be equivalent:

- (i) The product $X \times Y$ is strongly rectangular.
- (ii) Each finite open cover of $X \times Y$ has a locally finite refinement by co-zero rectangles.
- (iii) For each closed subset F and each open set U of $X \times Y$ with $F \subset U$, there is a locally finite collection W by cozero rectangles s.t. $F \subset \cup W \subset U$.
- (iv) $X \times Y$ is normal and for each zero-set F and each co-zero-set U of $X \times Y$ with $F \subset U$, there is a locally finite collection W by co-zero rectangles such that $F \subset \cup W \subset U$.
- (v) There exists a continuous map

$$f: X \times Y \rightarrow [0,1] \text{ such that } f(x,y) = \sum_{t \in T} g_t(x)h_t(y)$$

where $g_t: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $h_t: Y \rightarrow [0,1]$ are continuous.

IV. MODIFIED GAMES

We define the topological games $G(I, X)$ with a slight change as follows: Each topological space considered in this paper is assumed to be a Hausdorff space. N denotes the set of all natural numbers and m denotes an infinite cardinal number. Also let $L = \{E_i \mid E_i \text{ is closed subsets of } X\}$.

There are two players P and E . Player P chooses a closed set E_1 of X with $E_1 \in L$ and player E chooses an open set U_1 of X with $E_1 \subset U_1$ [5].

Again, player P chooses a closed set E_2 of X with $E_2 \in L$ and player E chooses an open set U_2 of X with $E_2 \subset U_2$ and so on.

The infinite sequence $\langle E_1, U_1, E_2, U_2, \dots \rangle$ is played by $G(L, X)$. Player P wins the play $\langle E_1, U_2, E_2, U_2, \dots \rangle$ if $\{U_n \mid n \in N\}$ covers X , otherwise player E wins.

A finite sequence $\langle E_1, U_1, \dots, E_n, U_n \rangle$ of subsets in X is said to be admissible for $G(L, X)$ if the infinite sequence $\langle E_1, U_1, \dots, E_n, U_n, \emptyset, \emptyset, \dots \rangle$ is a play of $G(L, X)$.

A function s is said to be a strategy for player P in $G(L, X)$ if the domain of S consists of the void sequence \emptyset and the finite sequence $\langle U_1, \dots, U_n \rangle$ of open sets in X and if $s(\emptyset)$ and $s(U_1, \dots, U_n)$ are closed in X and belong to L .

A strategy s for player P in the game $G(L, X)$ is said to be winning if he wins each play $\langle E_1, U_1, E_2, U_2, \dots \rangle$ in (L, X) such that $E_1 = S(\varphi)$ and $E_{n+1} = S(U_1, \dots, U_n)$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

We denote the following:

DL - The class of all spaces which have a discrete closed cover consisting of members of L .

FL - The class of all spaces which have a finite closed cover consisting of members of L .

C - The class of all compact spaces.

C_m - The class of m -compact space.

I_1, I_2 - Arbitrary classes of spaces possessing hereditary property s.t.

$I_1 \times I_2 = \{X \times Y : X \in I_1 \text{ and } Y \in I_2\}$

V. GAMES OVER SOME SPECIAL PRODUCT SPACES

Firstly, we define the following two product spaces:

D- Product: A product space $X \times Y$ is said to be a D-product if for each closed set M of $X \times Y$ and each open set O of $X \times Y$ with $M \subset O$, there is a discrete collection J by closed rectangles in $X \times Y$ such that $M \subset \cup J \subset O$.

For a closed rectangle R in $X \times Y$, R' and R'' denote the projection of R into X and Y respectively. Thus, R is a closed rectangle in $X \times Y$ if R' and R'' are closed in X & Y and R is an open rectangle in $X \times Y$ if $R'R''$ are open in X and Y such that $R = R' \times R''$ [6].

C-Product: A product space $X \times Y$ is said to be a C-product if for each closed set M of $X \times Y$ and each open set O of $X \times Y$ with $M \subset O$ there is a countable collection J by closed rectangles in $X \times Y$ such that $M \subset \cup J \subset O$.

With the help of definition of D-product, we have,

Theorem: (1) Let X and Y be spaces such that $X \times Y$ is a D-Product. If player P has winning strategies in $G(I_1, X)$ and (I_2, Y) , then he has a winning strategy in $G(D(I_1 \times I_2), X \times Y)$.

Now we prove the following

Theorem: (2) Let X be a collection wise normal space and Y a subpar compact space with $\chi(Y) \leq m$. If player P has a winning strategy in $G(DC_m, X)$, then every open cover of $X \times Y$ with power $< m$ has a σ -discrete refinement by closed rectangles in $X \times Y$.

Proof: Let s be a winning strategy of player P in $G(DC_m, X)$. Let C be an arbitrary open cover of $X \times Y$ with $|C| \leq m$.

We construct:

- (i) a sequence $\{J_n : n > 0\}$ collections of closed rectangles in $X \times Y$;
 - (ii) sequence $\{\langle \mathfrak{R}_n, \langle \psi_n \rangle : n \geq 0\}$ of the pairs of collections R_n by closed rectangles in $X \times Y$;
 - (iii) the function $\psi_n : \mathfrak{R}_n \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}_{n-1}$; satisfying the following five conditions:
 - (a) J_n is σ -discrete in $X \times Y$.
 - (b) R_n is σ -discrete in $X \times Y$.
 - (c) Each $F \in J_n$ is contained in some $G \in C$.
 - (d) If $(x, y) \in R_{n-1} \in \mathfrak{R}_{n-1}$ and $(x, y) \in \cup J_n$.
- Then there is $R_n \in \mathfrak{R}_n$ such that $(x, y) \in R_n$ and $\psi_n(R_n) = R_{n-1}$.
- (e) for an $R \in \mathfrak{R}_n$, Let $U_n = X - R$ and $U_k = X - (\psi_{k+1} \circ \dots \circ \psi_n(R))'$, for $1 \leq k \leq n-1$.

Then the finite sequence $\langle E_1, U_1, \dots, E_n, U_n \rangle$ is admissible for $G(DC_m, X)$.

Let $J_0 = \{\varphi\}$ and $\mathfrak{R}_0 = \{X \times Y\}$.

We suppose that the above $\{J_i : i < n\}$ and $\{\langle R_i, \psi_i \rangle : i \leq n\}$ are already constructed. We pick an $R \in \mathfrak{R}_n$.

Let $\langle E_1, U_1, \dots, E_n, U_n \rangle$ be the admissible sequence in $G(DC_m, X)$.

Hence there is a discrete collection $\{C_\alpha : \alpha \in \Omega(R)\}$ by m -compact closed sets in R such that $s(U_1, \dots, U_n) \cap R' = \cup \{C_\alpha : \alpha \in \Omega(R)\}$.

We can choose discrete collection $\{W_\alpha : \alpha \in \Omega(R)\}$ of open sets in R' s.t. $C_\alpha \subset W_\alpha$, for all $\alpha \in \Omega(R)$.

Since C_α is m -compact, $|C| < m$, $\chi(Y) \leq m$ and R' is subparacompact.

There is a collection $J_{n+1}^\alpha = \{C_l U^{\alpha, l} \times H : l = 1, \dots, K \text{ and } (k)\}$ and by closed rectangle in R , which satisfying the following four conditions:

- (i) Each $U^{\alpha,i}$ is open in R' .
- (2) $C \left\{ U^{\alpha,i} : i = 1, \dots, K \right\} W$.
- (3) Each CI $U^{\alpha,i} \times H_\lambda$ is contained in some $G \in C$.
- (4) $\{H : ()\}$ is a σ -discrete closed cover of R'' . Then $J_{n+1}^\alpha(R) = \{J_{n+1}^\alpha : \}$ is a σ -discrete in $X \times Y$.
 Put $R = \left\{ CI W - \left\{ U_{n+1}^\alpha : 1 \leq i \leq K \right\} \times H \right\}$, for all (k) .
 Again put $\bar{R} = \left(R' - \left\{ W_\alpha : \alpha \in (R) \right\} \right) \times R''$

Moreover, we put $R_{n+1}(R) = \{\bar{R} \cup \{R^\alpha : ()\} \text{ and } (R)\}$.

Then $R_{n+1}(R)$ is also σ -discrete collection by closed rectangles in R .

We set $J_{n+1} = \{J_{n+1}(R) : R \in \mathfrak{R}_n\}$ and $\mathfrak{R}_{n+1} = \cup \{R_{n+1}(R) : R \in \mathfrak{R}_n\}$.

The function $\psi_n : \mathfrak{R}_{n+1} \rightarrow R_n$ defined as $\psi_{n+1} : (\mathfrak{R}_{n+1})(R) = (R)$ for all $R \in \mathfrak{R}$.

From (a), J_{n+1} and \mathfrak{R}_{n+1} are σ -discrete in $X \times Y$.

The conditions (a) and (b) are satisfied.

By (3), the the condition (c) is also satisfied.

The conditions (d) and (e) are very clear.

Let $J = \cup \{J_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

We can easily show that J is a cover of $X \times Y$. Therefore, J is a σ -discrete refinement of C by closed rectangles in $X \times Y$.

With the consequences of the above theorem and by assuming PC_m to be the class of all product spaces with the first factor being non-compact, the following results can be obtained easily.

(R₁) Let X be a collection wise normal space and Y and a subparacompact space with $\chi(Y) \leq m$. If player P has a winning strategy in $G(DC_m, X)$, then $X \times Y$ is a D -product.

(R₂) Let X be a paracompact space and Y be a subparacompact space.

IF player P has a winning strategy is $G(DC, X)$, then $X \times Y$ is subparacompact.

(R₃) Let X be a collection wise normal space and Y be a subparacomact space with $\chi(Y) \leq m$. If player P has a winning strategy in $G(DC_m, X)$, then he has a winning strategy in $G(D(PC_{m,m}), X \times Y)$.

VI. FUZZY GAME

A game is determined by information, decisions and goals. But human notions (ideas) and decisions are fuzzy. For, a man with immense entropy functions may err, set right and understanding a little may increases his understanding in the pursuit of some knowledge. Therefore, in a game, perfect information, decisions & goals may not be feasible. We are therefore led to the introduction of fuzzy games.

Let $G = (N, v)$ be a nonfuzzy game of the set $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ of n players in which $v : S \rightarrow R$ is a real valid function (characteristic function) from a family of coalition $S \subset N$ to the set of real numbers R . Hence $v(A)$ means the gain which a coalition. A can acquire only through the action of A , the coalition A can be specified by the characteristic function τ^A as follows:

$$\tau^A(i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \in A; \\ 0 & \text{if } i \notin A. \end{cases}$$

A rate of participation $\tau^A(i)$ of a player i is defined by

$\tau^A(i) = 1$, if a player i participates in A and

$\tau^A(i) = 0$, if a player i does not not participate in A .

Consequently, a coalition A is represented by

$$= (\tau^A(1), \tau^A(2), \dots, \tau^A(n)).$$

A fuzzy coalition τ is defined as a coalition in which a player I can participate with a rate of participation $\tau_i \in [0, 1]$ instead of $\{0, 1\}$. The characteristic function nor coalitional worth function of a

fuzzy game is a real valued function $f: [0,1]^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which specifies a real number $f(\tau)$ for any fuzzy coalition τ .

This fuzzy game is denoted by $FG = (N, f)$. By obtaining this fuzzy game, we can have the corresponding results of the previous section easily which may produce better results.

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